

Full Paper

Highly efficient copper sulfide-based near-infrared photothermal agents: Exploring the limits of macroscopic heat conversion

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Abstract

Among the foreseeable therapeutic approaches at the cellular level, nanoplatform-driven photothermal therapy is a thriving tool for the selective eradication of malignant tissues with minimal side effects to healthy ones. Hence, chemically versatile, near-infrared absorbing plasmonic nanoparticles as efficient photothermal agents are distinctly appealing and most sought after. In this work, we develop and optimize a straightforward method to synthesize monodisperse pegylated copper sulfide nanoparticles of pure covellite – CuS – phase, featuring strong localized surface plasmonic resonance absorption in the near-infrared and flexible surface chemistry, imparted by monomethyl ether polyethylene glycol molecules. These nanoparticles show a remarkable photothermal heat conversion efficiency (HCE) of 71.4 %, which is amongst the highest for CuS systems and rivals that of plasmonic noble metal nanostructures. Moreover, through a critical evaluation and mathematical modelling of the material's properties and measurement methodology, we assess that the calculated HCE values drastically depend on experimental conditions such as wavelength-dependent solvent absorption properties, sol concentration and optical path. These findings are of paramount relevance to the photothermal community, since they call for a standardization of the procedure for the evaluation of the HCE of proposed photothermal agents, in order to make the reported values universally and reliably comparable.

1. Introduction

The goal of nano-therapeutic approaches for the thermal treatment of solid tumors is to locally raise the temperature in malignant cells to the 42-48 °C range¹⁻⁴ in order to promote controlled cell death (apoptosis rather than necrosis).⁵⁻⁶ In photothermal therapy (PTT), such temperature increase is achieved by exploiting photothermal agents that can convert light to

heat.¹ The appeal of PTT lies in the possibility of confining the cytotoxic effects of the generated heat to the area under treatment, simultaneously promoting the accumulation of the photothermal agents at the tumor site⁷ and focusing the external stimulus (light) exclusively on the zone of interest.

One main limitation of present-day PTT is the use of visible light that scarcely penetrates into biological tissues, due to scattering and absorption phenomena⁸. To alleviate this shortcoming, a number of near-infrared (NIR) triggered photothermal agents were proposed, as NIR radiation can penetrate deeper in biological tissues allowing for sub-cutaneous tumor treatment.^{1, 8} Among other photothermal agents, plasmonic nanoparticles are intensively studied, with their characteristic localized surface plasmon resonance (LSPR) being a driving force behind the efficient application of modern PTT. LSPR is the resonant response in the collective motion of free charge carriers that is prompted by light when its frequency matches the natural oscillation frequency of the free carriers in the nanoparticles.⁹⁻¹¹ The light absorption is followed by de-excitation processes, leading to the release of the absorbed energy to the surroundings, with some of it in the form of heat *via* non-radiative pathways (photothermal effect).¹²

Although many gold-based nanoparticles¹³⁻¹⁸ display strong NIR LSPR absorption properties^{3, 15, 19} and corresponding heat conversion efficiencies (HCE) as high as 80 %, ^{20, 21} they are costly to produce and their size often exceeds 100 nm, a contentious trait in the context of most biological applications.²²⁻²⁴ Moreover, prolonged exposure to heat can result in the modification of the gold nanoparticles' morphology, leading to changes in their LSPR absorption profile and a partial or complete loss of the heat conversion properties.²⁵ These limitations are overcome with copper sulfide plasmonic nanoparticles as, albeit they possess lower free carrier density compared to gold-based photothermal agents (10^{20} - 10^{22} cm⁻³ vs 10^{23} cm⁻³),^{11, 26, 27} they absorb light over a broad NIR spectral range, are smaller, stable under

prolonged optical excitation, significantly less expensive to synthesize, and display nearly analogous heat conversion capabilities compared to gold nanoparticles.²⁸

Being an intrinsic p-type semiconductor, copper sulfide features free holes in the valence band (VB) that are delocalized in the nanoparticle.¹¹ Among the different copper sulfide compounds of generic formula Cu_{2-x}S , covellite (CuS) has the highest free-hole density and a strong LSPR absorption. This leads to high HCE values,²⁹⁻³³ which in turn translate into a large net heat delivery in the area of treatment.

The above-mentioned features of CuS nanoparticles have fostered investigation on their possible use, either alone or in combination with different moieties for the development of complex nano-systems, especially in the bio-medical field.³⁴⁻³⁷ In this vein, although approaches for the direct preparation of hydrophilic CuS nanoparticles have already been proposed,³⁸⁻⁴¹ they usually yield systems with a relatively low plasmonic response and/or a pre-determined surface chemistry that cannot be easily tailored post-synthesis. Therefore, it is apparent that having access to CuS nanoparticles simultaneously featuring dispersibility in water, high heat conversion capabilities and a finely tunable surface chemistry would represent a tremendous advantage to their biomedical applications.

In this study, CuS nanoparticles were synthesized in water *via* a green approach that exploits the mild coordinating capabilities of monomethyl ether polyethylene glycol (mPEG). Small, pure phase CuS nanoparticles possessing remarkable heat conversion capabilities and a tailorable surface chemistry were obtained by carefully tuning the reaction parameters. Importantly, theoretical modelling of the optical properties of the system and its photothermal capabilities allowed for the identification of the limits of the macroscopic experimental methods for the HCE determination. This observation represents a pivotal conclusion on the importance of standardized HCE determination for diverse systems, since the performance of

newly developed photothermal agents is often calculated under different experimental conditions, making direct comparison between various reports difficult.

2. Results and discussion

2.1. CuS synthesis and reaction optimization.

The newly proposed approach for the synthesis of CuS nanoparticles, which utilizes mPEG as the coordinating ligand, was optimized thoroughly exploring the effect of the reaction parameters on the properties of the produced particles (Table S1). Over the range of various parameters affecting the nanoparticles' optical and morphological features, the S/Cu ratio displayed the greatest effect (Figure 1A and B). The use of a S/Cu ratio of 0.75 or 1.00 only influenced the reaction yield (as inferred from the different intensities of the absorption spectra), but had no effect on the LSPR band profile or the nanoparticle crystalline structure (covellite CuS, PDF #01-078-2121). The nanoparticles synthesized with a S/Cu ratio of 1.00 have a quasi-spherical shape, with a size of (7.2 ± 0.7) nm (Figure 1C). Increasing S/Cu to 2.00 led to an increase of the LSPR peak intensity and to the growth of larger crystallites (as indicated by narrower reflections in the X-ray powder diffraction (XRD) pattern - Figure 1B) with different morphologies (Figure S1). Further increasing S/Cu to 4.00 led to a dramatic drop of the LSPR peak intensity and the appearance of a secondary phase (tentatively assigned to digenite Cu_9S_5), accompanied by a loss of colloidal stability of the sample with noticeable precipitation few minutes after the synthesis.

Interestingly, tunability of the LSPR peak position is achievable by varying the reaction temperature. Specifically, fixing S/Cu to 1.00 and changing the reaction temperature in the 40-100 °C range allowed for shifting of the maximum of the LSPR-related absorption from 1050 to 950 nm (Figure 1D), without affecting the crystallinity of the sample (Figure S2). X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) measurements (Figure S3 and Table S2) and the

elaboration of the absorption spectra *via* the Tauc approach⁴² (Figure S4) ruled out changes of copper oxidation state, compositional variations between the samples, and differences in the band gap value as possible causes for this trend. However, TEM observations showed a gradual increase of the nanoparticles' size with increasing the reaction temperature from 40 to 100 °C (Figure S5), thus explaining the hypsochromic LSPR peak shift since larger nanoparticles have a blue-shifted plasmonic resonance compared to smaller ones.²⁶

The effects of mPEG amount and pH of the reaction mixture were also explored. It was observed that, in the tested range, the amount of mPEG used for controlling the growth of CuS nanoparticles has little influence on the final properties of the sample (Figure S6); instead, increasing the pH of the reaction mixture above 5 prompts the appearance of a secondary phase likely related to the presence of Cu(OH)₂ as a starting material (Figure S7). The sample synthesized at 80 °C, with S/Cu = 1.00, in the presence of 4 g of mPEG at pH 4.6 (from here on CuS nanoparticles) was selected for further studies being the best in terms of optical, morphological, and structural properties.

2.2. Surface chemistry of CuS nanoparticles.

The presence of mPEG molecules tethered to the nanoparticle surface was confirmed by employing SEM and taking advantage of the different penetration depths exhibited by electrons with different kinetic energies, *i.e.* subjected to different accelerating voltages (Figure 1E).⁴³ This technique relies on the fact that, when travelling through the material, the accelerated (*i.e.* primary) electrons with larger kinetic energy can withstand a higher number of collision events before being eventually stopped. Hence, higher energy electrons can generate secondary electrons (used to obtain the SEM micrographs) at greater depth. On the contrary, electrons subjected to a low enough accelerating voltage lose their kinetic energy mainly due to the interaction with the superficial layers of organic material, where the majority of secondary electrons are thus generated. Indeed, exploiting this approach, a

polymeric coating was directly observed on the nanoparticles. Notably, no polymer could be observed on the surface of nanoparticles prepared without mPEG (Figure S8).

A unique feature of the prepared CuS nanoparticles is the remarkable control that can be exerted over their surface chemistry. In order to prove the system's versatility in this regard, mPEG molecules on the CuS nanoparticles' surface were ligand exchanged with five species having considerably different chemical character (PEG-thiol (PEG-SH), glutathione (GSH), bovine serum albumin (BSA), polyacrylic acid (PAA), and cysteine – Figure 2). The exchange procedure is straightforward and simply involves stirring the synthesized CuS nanoparticles at room temperature for 45 min in the presence of the ligand moiety of choice. These mild conditions are ensured by the moderate interaction exhibited by mPEG molecules with the surface of CuS nanoparticles, which guarantees a complete and fast exchange for more strongly interacting species.

The success of the surface modification was confirmed through Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy and thermogravimetric measurements, both of which showed the presence of the respective moiety exchanged for mPEG (a thorough discussion of the FTIR spectra and the thermograms – Figure S9 – is reported in the Supplementary Information). Most importantly, the optical properties stemming from the plasmonic nature of the material are not compromised by the ligand exchange procedure, as proved by the absorption spectra (Figure 2G) recorded on the colloidal stable samples (Figure 2H). The retaining of the optical features after the ligand exchange procedure makes these nanoparticles extremely attractive for a number of applications that require an on-demand tailorable surface chemistry. As proven by dynamic light scattering (DLS) measurements and photographs of the sols (Figure 2C, D and S10), the CuS nanoparticles decorated with different molecules show good dispersibility and colloidal stability not only in distilled water, but also in phosphate buffered saline (PBS 0.1x) and PBS with 10 % of fetal bovine serum (FBS). The hydrodynamic

diameter (D_H) of the particles exchanged with the selected ligands varies with the size of the moiety tethered to the surface, ranging in water from approximately 10 to 56 nm in the case of cysteine and BSA, respectively (see Table S3 for a comprehensive overview of the DLS results). The colloidal stability featured by CuS nanoparticles in aqueous media is a pivotal aspect of the developed system as it brings these nanosystems closer to their foreseeable application in an actual biomedical context.

2.3. Calculation of CuS nanoparticles' heat conversion efficiency.

CuS nanoparticles (S/Cu = 1.00) exchanged with PEG-SH were selected for their outstanding colloidal stability (see Figure 2C and 2D) to assess the performance of the system as a photothermal agent by measuring its HCE. For the case under study, the theoretically estimated light scattering represents a negligible proportion of the total nanoparticle extinction in the spectral range of interest (806-970 nm, as explained below), a feature that makes CuS nanoparticles advantageous photothermal agents as they are capable of almost total conversion of absorbed light to heat. Moreover, because of the broad LSPR absorption band, the photothermal effect of CuS nanoparticles can be triggered using a wide range of wavelengths, an asset in the context of PTT. Following this reasoning, we evaluated the HCE of the system at two different wavelengths, namely 806 and 970 nm, recording the heating-cooling curves for an aqueous CuS nanoparticle sol (Figure 3A and 3C) according to the procedure outlined in the ESI (Scheme S1). It is worth noting that the heating properties are retained by the particles upon the repeated heating-cooling cycles, thus putting into evidence the good physicochemical stability of the investigated system (Figure S11). The experimental data were treated using the approach introduced by Roper *et al.*⁴⁴ obtaining HCE values of $(71.4 \pm 5.8) \%$ and $(58.2 \pm 3.1) \%$ at 806 and 970 nm, respectively, among the highest values reported in the literature for chalcogenide-based photothermal agents (Table S4). To investigate the possible influence of different capping ligands on the nanoparticles' HCE, we

prepared a fresh batch of CuS nanoparticles, modified their surface with PEG-SH, BSA and GSH, and measured their HCE in water under 806 nm wavelength of excitation (wavelength at which the absorption of the solvent is minimally influencing the measurements). The HCE values calculated for these nanoparticles are: CuS-PEG-SG – $(66.9 \pm 4.2) \%$; CuS-BSA – $(64.9 \pm 3.3) \%$; CuS-GSH – $(65.9 \pm 2.0) \%$ (Figure S12). The agreement of these values, within experimental error, between themselves and with our previous estimate not only definitively confirms the intrinsically high HCE values of our nanoparticles, but also ruled out any influence of the capping ligand and confirmed negligible batch-to-batch variability.

Interestingly, the results seem to suggest a wavelength-dependent behavior of the system. These values were calculated correcting the power on the target for the cuvette absorption and considering the heat capacity of the system as a sum of the contribution from the different parts of which it is composed, *i.e.* glass cuvette and CuS nanoparticle sol (Table S5). To further clarify the observed HCE dependence on the excitation wavelength, additional measurements in heavy water (D_2O) were performed (Figure 3B and 3D), since D_2O displays similar optical response at both 806 and 970 nm (see below). Noteworthy, the HCE values obtained in D_2O at the two wavelengths are very close to each other and to the value obtained in H_2O under 806 nm excitation. These results point out an important dependence of HCE on the experimental parameters, particularly the intrinsic solvent absorbance at the excitation wavelength. To gain a better insight into such dependence, we extended our investigation also implementing a theoretical model of the system.

2.4. Theoretical discussion of the photothermal effect.

Electrodynamic calculations for CuS nanoparticles of 7 nm coated with PEG-SH ($S/Cu = 1.00$), describing the permittivity of CuS through the Drude model, reproduced well the measured absorption spectrum (Figure S13). Moreover, it was estimated that small CuS nanoparticles exhibit very low scattering (less than 0.2 % of the total nanoparticle extinction

in the 806 to 970 nm wavelength range, Figure S14). Consequently, this sets ground to assume that the plasmon energy is fully dissipated to heat through the collisions of mobile carriers with the atomic lattice. This reasoning would suggest that the HCE, as defined by Roper *et al.*,⁴⁴ for CuS nanoparticles should approach values of 100 %, as there is no direct electron promotion through the CuS bandgap at these wavelengths and assuming that there are no other dissipation channels for the electromagnetic energy - such as photocatalytic processes at the nanoparticles' surfaces.

However, upon modelling the behavior of the photothermal agents, we noticed that the HCE value is not only significantly lower than a 100 % (consistent with many other reports on different materials)^{28, 45-47} but it is strongly influenced by the excitation wavelength and, in general, by the experimental system employed. The observed discrepancies for the different excitation wavelengths foremost correlate with the properties of the medium in which the nanoparticles are dispersed, and stem from the practical limitations of using macroscopic measurement tools (either calorimetric⁴⁴ or optical⁴⁸) to quantify intrinsically microscopic properties. Hence, following is a discussion on the effect that the choice of the excitation wavelength and the optical properties of the solvent have on the determined HCE value.

The conclusions that are drawn help to reliably assess the potential of the presented CuS nanoparticles as multi-wavelength photothermal agents and, more generally, suggest the necessity of a standardized protocol for the determination and comparison of HCE calculated for different systems.

The commonly used HCE calculation procedure described by Roper *et al.*⁴⁴ uses the identity

$$\eta = \frac{Q_{\text{ext}} - Q_0}{I(1 - 10^{-A_\lambda})} \quad (1)$$

where Q_{ext} is the external heat injected into the nanoparticle dispersion, Q_0 is the heat dissipated by the solvent alone, and at the denominator is the radiated power extinguished by the nanoparticles alone, all measured in the system at thermal equilibrium. We calculated the heat inputs in the numerator by measuring the temperature T that the system achieves at the thermal equilibrium, by the expression

$$Q = hA(T - T_{\text{room}}) \quad (2)$$

where T_{room} is the room temperature and hA is the product of the heat transfer coefficient and the area of the sample in contact with the environment, calculated as

$$hA = \frac{\sum_i m_i c_{p,i}}{\tau} \quad (3)$$

where m and c_p are the mass and heat capacity of the different materials that compose the sample, running through index i , and τ is the sample time constant, obtained by fitting the cooling part of the heating curves. This last variable provides information on how fast the system loses energy to the environment.

The heat inputs in Equation 1 can be modelled through the mathematical description of the beam attenuation ($I/I_0 = 10^{-A_\lambda}$) to then use the Beer-Lambert law to describe the absorbance of the system (A_λ) in terms of the materials' microscopic properties. In particular, the nanoparticles' interaction with light is described by their molar extinction coefficient (composed of absorption and scattering: $\varepsilon_\lambda = \varepsilon_\lambda^{\text{abs}} + \varepsilon_\lambda^{\text{scat}}$), molar concentration (c), and beam optical path (L). Considering an ideal dispersion of perfect plasmonic absorbers, such that no radiation is scattered across the beam path ($\varepsilon_\lambda^{\text{scat}} = 0$), we can write an expression for the HCE of an idealized system that is helpful to illustrate some characteristics of this metric:

$$\eta = \frac{I\left(1 - 10^{-(\mu_\lambda + \varepsilon_\lambda^{\text{abs}} c)L}\right) - I\left(1 - 10^{-\mu_\lambda L}\right)}{I\left(1 - 10^{-\varepsilon_\lambda^{\text{abs}} cL}\right)} = 10^{-\mu_\lambda L} \quad (4)$$

noting by μ_λ the wavelength-dependent decadic attenuation coefficient of the solvent. By expressing the HCE in this form, it is apparent that the experimentally determined HCE value is in general wavelength-dependent due to both nanoparticle's and solvent's attenuation properties, and actually only depends on the solvent's properties when assuming no scattering. One can understand this expression, obtained under some assumptions of sample ideality, as a maximum theoretical value for the HCE as it is commonly defined. In such a situation, we would obtain a perfect (*i.e.* 100 %) HCE only if the solvent does not absorb ($\mu_\lambda = 0$). Thus, any difference in solvent absorption at different wavelengths will impact the calculated HCE, an effect similar to the one already reported for different systems.⁴⁴ This is confirmed by the fact that from the experimental measurements performed in D₂O - which has a similarly low absorption at both wavelengths - the estimated HCE values at 806 and 970 nm are comparable to the one obtained at 806 nm in H₂O. Indeed, the higher optical absorption of H₂O at 970 nm results in a lower calculated HCE, even though the nanoparticles' absorption-to-extinction ratio is almost identical at the two wavelengths, and their absorption is actually higher at 970 nm than at 806 nm (Figure S14 and 4E). It is noteworthy that, with the exception of the laser power, when expressing Equation 1 using the Beer-Lambert law (Equation 4), all the physical parameters of the system appear as exponents in the HCE, so that small changes in these variables lead to substantially different HCE values. In particular, the heat delivered after light absorption of the solvent by itself can easily mask the heating effect of the nanoparticles when their concentration is low. Additionally, a long optical path (L) strengthens the nonlinearity of the HCE calculation. Only in the limit of L approaching

zero, the expression could be linearized in the microscopic parameters and be approximated to $\eta \approx \varepsilon_{\lambda}^{\text{abs}} / (\varepsilon_{\lambda}^{\text{abs}} + \varepsilon_{\lambda}^{\text{scat}})$, losing the impact of the solvent in the measurement.

In order to provide additional support to these arguments, we calculated the HCE of CuS nanoparticles both using the fully analytical expression of Equation 4 and analyzing the thermal data of a simulated heating experiment, using the conventional cooling time procedure⁴⁴ (Figure 4, additional details in ESI – Figure S15). Considering a simplified description of the cuvette used in the experimental setup (sketch in Figure 4A), the simulated heating experiment provides a reasonable agreement with the experimental data (Figure 4B-D - Table S6). These simulations were performed by solving the heat diffusion equation in the simplified system, with the whole nanoparticle dispersion being a homogeneous source of heat (mimicking the stirring conditions of the experiment), and with its magnitude calculated *via* the Beer-Lambert law. This type of photo-heating is highly collective⁴⁹ and suitable for the generation of heat over relatively large volumes, making it of interest for many bio-related applications.^{50, 51} The above-reported results illustrate how, even in a simulated system that does not account for energy dissipation mechanisms other than plasmonic absorption converted into heat, the computation of HCE depends strongly on the solvent absorption profile (Figure 4E). Consequently, this approach depends on the measurement conditions (*e.g.* the optical path – Figure 4D, analytical HCE) that can mask the effect of the nanoparticles' heating. In this regard, it is of interest to observe that the HCE values calculated in D₂O show almost equal values for both tested wavelengths. Instead, when considering H₂O as the solvent, there is a significant difference between the values obtained at 806 and 970 nm, in accordance with what observed in the experiment.

Some further comments are necessary to clarify why the HCE values obtained with the numerical simulations are consistently lower than the analytical maximum results. Given that

the system defined in the computational model does not include scattering, nor other sources of energy loss other than heating, one would expect that the HCE values obtained with it would be arbitrarily close to the analytical values. The reason for this discrepancy, which is spelled out in greater detail in the Supplementary Information, is twofold: first, we adopted the experimental measuring procedure in the simulated system. Thus, even though we have access to the exact heat input in the system, we limit ourselves to obtain it through the temperature measured inside the system at equilibrium. Second, this procedure groups the sample (including cuvette and other elements) into an effective value of its heat transfer coefficient, through Equation 3. Depending on the temperature distribution over the full setup at thermal equilibrium and on choices in the computation of Equation 3, one could introduce a systematic undercounting of the heat input, especially if the sample is not placed in a vacuum chamber.

3. Conclusions

We reported the green synthesis of small, quasi-spherical, and pegylated CuS nanoparticles with a HCE value of 71.4% - evaluated in water upon laser excitation at 806 nm - making this system one of the best performing sulfide-based photothermal agent reported so far. A specific merit of the proposed green synthesis approach resides in the dispersibility of the CuS nanoparticles in water and aqueous media mimicking biological fluids, along with ~~and~~ the possibility of easily tailoring their surface using a variety of molecules. A prominent advantage of these nanoparticles as photothermal agents is represented by the minimal amount of optical energy scattered or re-emitted through luminescence, leading to nearly absolute conversion of light into heat. Altogether, the properties featured by the developed CuS nanoparticles in terms of small size, size monodispersion, colloidal stability in aqueous and biological media, tunability of the surface chemistry and outstanding light-to-heat transduction capability makes the system an ideal candidate for a stand-alone photothermal

agent and/or a valuable building block for the preparation of multipurpose nanomaterials for biomedical applications.

Another relevant finding for the photothermal community, stemming from a critical evaluation and mathematical modelling of the material's properties and measurement methodology, is that calculated HCE values drastically depend on the parameters characterizing the experimental setup used to determine them. In particular, the dependence on the solvent absorption and other experimental conditions, such as sol concentration and optical path, calls for some degree of standardization on the measurement of HCE for potential photothermal agents in order to make the data reported universally and reliably comparable.

4. Experimental Section

Chemicals

Copper chloride dihydrate ($\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, Alfa Aesar, +98 %), monomethyl ether polyethylene glycol MW 5,000 (mPEG, Aldrich, 99 %), sodium sulfide nonahydrate ($\text{Na}_2\text{S} \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$, Aldrich, 98 %), and ethanol (Commercial Alcohols, 100 %) were all used as received without further purification. The working solutions were freshly prepared with de-ionized water and used within one week from their preparation. $\text{Na}_2\text{S} \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ solution was stored at 2-4 °C.

Synthesis of CuS nanoparticles

Copper sulfide nanoparticles were synthesized *via* a green and newly developed one-pot approach. In a typical procedure, 8 mL of a $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ aqueous solution (12.5 mM) was introduced in a 50 mL three necked round bottom flask along with 4 g of mPEG and a magnetic stir bar. After the complete dissolution of the polymer under stirring at room temperature, the flask was placed in a pre-heated oil bath at 80 °C. After 3 min, 100 μL of a 1 M $\text{Na}_2\text{S} \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ aqueous solution (S/Cu = 1.00) was injected in the reaction mixture. This step was followed by a fast darkening of the solution that eventually became dark green. The reaction was allowed to proceed for 5 min. The reaction flask was then quenched in cold water, and the reaction mixture was transferred to a 50 mL centrifuge tube. Then, 20 mL of isopropyl alcohol were added and the synthesized nanoparticles were collected by means of centrifugation (20 min, 6,000 g). Eventually, the nanoparticles were re-dispersed in 5 mL of de-ionized water and stored at 4 °C for further characterization.

We investigated the effect of the different reaction parameters on the properties of copper sulfide nanoparticles. Specifically, we studied the effect of sulfur-to-copper ratio (S/Cu), mPEG amount, reaction temperature, and pH. A summary of the different parameters explored throughout this study for the synthesis of CuS nanoparticles is reported in the Supplementary Information (Table S1).

Ligand exchange procedure

The surface of the CuS nanoparticles was modified through a ligand exchange procedure using five different species, each displaying specific chemical properties. To accomplish this, a fresh batch of CuS nanoparticles was synthesized starting from 32 mL of $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ aqueous solution (12.5 mM) and adjusting the amount of the other chemical species accordingly. After the purification step, the CuS nanoparticles were dispersed in 12 mL of water and split in six aliquots. Five of them were transferred to 20 mL scintillation vials along with 1 mL of distilled water and different amounts of PEG-thiol (PEG-SH MW 2,000 - 14 mg), cysteine (30 mg), glutathione (GSH - 50 mg), polyacrylic acid (PAA MW 130,000 - 100 mg), and bovine serum albumin (BSA - 50 mg), respectively. Each sol was sonicated for 1 min and stirred at room temperature for 45 min. Afterwards each CuS nanoparticle batch was transferred to a centrifuge tube, 40 mL of isopropanol was added and the particles were centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 20 min at 6 °C. The purification step was repeated at least two more times. In the case of cysteine, after the first precipitation, the pH of the aqueous CuS nanoparticle sol was adjusted to 9-10 before adding isopropanol. Each batch was eventually re-dispersed in 2 mL of distilled water or dried overnight for further characterization.

Characterization

The absorption spectra were acquired with a Varian Cary 5000 spectrophotometer using a double beam configuration and 1 cm optical path length quartz cuvettes. A scan speed of 600 nm min^{-1} with 1 nm of spectral resolution was used to record the spectra over the 300-1100 nm range. The CuS nanoparticle crystalline structure was probed by means of powder XRD with a Bruker D8 Advance Diffractometer using Cu $K\alpha$ monochromatic radiation with a Bragg-Brentano theta-2theta configuration. A scan step of 0.05° and 6 s step^{-1} acquisition time was employed, recording the spectra over the $25\text{-}60^\circ$ range. The morphology of the samples was analyzed using Transmission and Scanning Electron Microscopy (TEM and

SEM), respectively, using JEOL-JEM 3010 TEM and a field emission gun (FEG) ZEISS-Sigma SEM microscopes. The surface chemistry of the nanoparticles was analyzed *via* Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy. The spectra were recorded on a ThermoFisher Scientific Nicolet 6700 spectrometer working in transmission mode with a resolution of 1 cm^{-1} over the $4000\text{-}800\text{ cm}^{-1}$ range. The surface chemistry along with the chemical composition of the nanoparticles was further investigated by means of XPS. The spectra were recorded on a VG ESCALAB 200i XL instrument, using an Al $K\alpha$ monochromatic source. The spectra were analyzed using CasaXPS[®] software. Dynamic light scattering measurements were performed on a Malvern Zetasizer Nano ZS[®]. Thermogravimetric (TG) measurements were performed on a TGA Q500/Discovery M instrument in an atmosphere of 90 % air and 10 % N₂ in the temperature range of 30-800 °C with a scan rate of 10 °C min^{-1} .

Heat conversion efficiency (HCE) evaluation

The heat conversion efficiency (η) of the CuS nanoparticles was evaluated by irradiating the nanoparticle aqueous sol contained in a 1x1 cm optical path “special optical glass” cuvette (Hellma Analytics) with either a 806 or 970 nm continuous wave laser (on target $P = 180\text{ mW}$, $P_d = 10.5\text{ W cm}^{-2}$). The local temperature increase in the cuvette was probed with a digital thermometer (equipped with a type-K thermocouple of 0.1 °C sensitivity). A reference thermocouple of the same type was placed in an empty 1x1 cm cuvette in order to account for a sizeable ambient temperature variation throughout the duration of experiments. A working volume of 1 mL of CuS nanoparticle aqueous sol was prepared either in distilled water (Millipore) or heavy water (99.9 %_{at} D; Aldrich) with an optical density (OD) in either solvent of approximately 0.16 and 0.23 at 806 and 970 nm laser excitation wavelengths, respectively. Sols were kept under continuous magnetic stirring (400 rpm) during the heating-cooling cycles.

Heating-cooling curves were obtained from three independent measurements for each of the studied conditions.

Computational methods

The heat evolution in the sol irradiated with laser light stems simultaneously from the heat conversion from CuS nanoparticles and water molecules. In this section we give a brief account of the models used in the numerical methods, which were solved using the Finite Element Method, as implemented in commercial package COMSOL. A more detailed description can be found in the Supplementary Information, including all relevant material parameters.

Optical absorption modelling. The NIR photons used to excite the semiconductor CuS nanoparticles do not have enough energy to promote direct electronic transitions. Therefore, the main heating mechanism is the excitation of LSPR and their ensuing energy dissipation through carrier collisions. The absorbance spectra of the CuS nanoparticles were reproduced by calculating the absorption of small spheres described by a permittivity $\varepsilon(\omega)$ modelled through the Drude model, yielding an estimate for their hole density of $N_h \approx 10^{22} \text{ cm}^{-3}$.

The optical response of CuS nanoparticles has been calculated within a classical framework, solving Maxwell's equations for isolated small spheres surrounded by a homogeneous matrix of non-absorbing dielectric.

Heat transfer modelling. We have considered a simplified physical system to numerically solve the heat equation, in which the effect of fluid dynamics in the cuvette is neglected and the study is limited to thermal diffusion. To account for both the nanoparticle dispersion and the thermal equalization that magnetic stirring provides in the experimental setup, we have imparted heat homogeneously to the whole solution during the time that the laser illuminates the sample, to then let the system cool by thermalizing with its environment. By replicating the heating and

cooling phases in the simulation, we are able to conduct the same measuring technique that the experiment relies on,⁴⁰ but in a simpler and fully controlled system.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Figure 1. S/Cu ratio has a major role in determining the CuS nanoparticles' optical (A), structural (B), and morphological features (sketches in A and Figure S1). The optimal balance between NIR absorption and size monodispersity (C) is obtained when S/Cu = 1, while changing the reaction temperature allows for the tuning of the LSPR peak position (D). SEM observations at different electron accelerating voltage permit to visualize directly the polymeric layer of mPEG on the CuS nanoparticles' surface (E – scale bars 200 nm). All optical absorption spectra (A) were recorded sampling 100 μ L of each purified sol and diluting it in 1.5 mL of distilled water.

Figure 2. The presence of mPEG or exchanged ligand molecules on the surface of CuS nanoparticles is confirmed by the comparison of the FTIR spectra of the samples with those of pristine ligand molecules (A i-vi). The vibrations observable in both the spectrum of the nanoparticles and the ligands are highlighted with grey shaded areas and the most relevant vibrations are indicated in the graphs. Importantly, the absorption properties of CuS nanoparticles are retained after the ligand exchange process, with minimal effects on the peak shape, position and intensity (B). All samples form stable sols in water (C). In the case of cysteine and GSH, to obtain an optically clear solution, the nanoparticles were dispersed in a 50 mM NaOH solution. All optical absorption spectra were recorded on samples prepared diluting 300 μL of each purified sol in 1.5 mL of distilled water. DLS measurements (D) performed on sols of each batch of CuS nanoparticles dispersed in distilled water (light blue), PBS 0.1x (green) and PBS 0.1x + 10 % FBS (orange) show a single distribution of the coated nanoparticles.

Figure 3. Heating-cooling curves recorded under 806 and 970 nm laser irradiation ($power = 0.18 \text{ W}$) for H₂O (**A**), D₂O (**B**) and CuS nanoparticle sols in the two solvents (**C** and **D**) were treated according to Roper's model to obtain the HCE value for the photothermal agents. In the insets, the fit of the cooling part is shown: the obtained heat-dissipation time (τ) was used to estimate the heat-transfer coefficient h in Equation S7.

Figure 4. Theoretical calculations of the HCE values were performed considering a 1 cm optical path (L) glass cuvette containing 1 g of pure solvent (H₂O or D₂O) or CuS nanoparticles' sols at a concentration (c) of $3 \cdot 10^{13} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ (**A** – case of H₂O). The power of the exciting laser beam was set to 0.18 W both for 806 and 970 nm. The simulated heating-cooling curves were obtained considering the temperature at the center of the volume of the sol (**B** and **C**). The corresponding HCE values (**D**) are calculated using Equation 4 (*analytical*) and using Roper's procedure considering the temperatures obtained in the simulation (*numerical*). In square brackets, analytical HCE values are reported for a shorter optical path (2 mm). The differences in HCE obtained in H₂O at 806 and 970 nm arise from the different absorption of the solvent at the two wavelengths (**E**). The flat absorption profile of D₂O throughout the optical range considerably minimizes the difference among calculated HCE values.

A study on copper sulfide nanoparticles as efficient light-to-heat converters operating in the near-infrared biological transparency window. First, a new facile and reliable process is described to synthesize monodisperse single phase (covellite) nanocrystals, with easily tailorable surface chemistry and suitable for photothermal therapy. Second, critical discussion of the characteristics and limitations of the currently used heat conversion efficiency estimation is presented.

Keywords: Copper Sulfide, Heat Conversion Efficiency, Plasmon Resonance, Photothermal Effect.

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Highly efficient copper sulfide-based near-infrared photothermal agents: Exploring the limits of macroscopic heat conversion

ToC figure

Supporting Information

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Synthetic parameters investigated

Table S1. Summary of the parameters investigated in this work for the optimization of the CuS nanoparticle synthesis approach. The parameters in bold italic are those whose values have been varied for each series of samples. The sample with gray background is the reference for all the series.

<i>Cu²⁺</i> , mmol	<i>Temperature</i> , °C	<i>pH</i>	<i>S/Cu</i>	<i>mPEG</i> , g
0.1	80	4.6	<i>0.75</i>	4.00
0.1	80	4.6	<i>1.00</i>	4.00
0.1	80	4.6	<i>2.00</i>	4.00
0.1	80	4.6	<i>4.00</i>	4.00
0.1	<i>40</i>	4.6	1.00	4.00
0.1	<i>60</i>	4.6	1.00	4.00
0.1	<i>90</i>	4.6	1.00	4.00
0.1	<i>100</i>	4.6	1.00	4.00
0.1	80	<i>2</i>	1.00	4.00
0.1	80	<i>3</i>	1.00	4.00
0.1	80	<i>6</i>	1.00	4.00
0.1	80	<i>8</i>	1.00	4.00
0.1	80	<i>10</i>	1.00	4.00
0.1	80	4.6	1.00	<i>0.25</i>
0.1	80	4.6	1.00	<i>0.50</i>
0.1	80	4.6	1.00	<i>1.00</i>
0.1	80	4.6	1.00	<i>2.00</i>
0.1	80	4.6	1.00	<i>8.00</i>

Setup for the experimental evaluation of the heat conversion efficiency (HCE)

Scheme S1. Set-up used for the determination of the CuS nanoparticles' HCE. In the “top view”, denoted A, we indicate the area of the cuvette section, which is the surface through which the heat is exchanged with the environment.

Computational methods

The heat evolution in the sol irradiated with laser light stems simultaneously from the heat conversion from CuS nanoparticles and water molecules. To support the discussion of our results, it is useful to illustrate the physical mechanism through which the CuS nanoparticles heat and describe it theoretically.

Optical absorption modelling

CuS is a semiconductor with a large free hole density. The near-infrared (NIR) photons used to excite the CuS nanoparticles do not have enough energy to promote direct electronic transitions. Therefore, the main heating mechanism is the excitation of collective carrier oscillations according to the localized surface plasmon resonance (LSPR) effect and their ensuing dissipation through carrier collisions. This being considered, the absorbance spectra of the nanoparticles are well reproduced by modelling the permittivity $\varepsilon(\omega)$ of the CuS nanoparticles through the Drude model (Figure S10):

$$\varepsilon(\omega) = \varepsilon_{\infty} - \frac{\omega_p^2}{\omega(\omega + i\gamma)}; \quad \omega_p^2 = \frac{N_h e^2}{\varepsilon_0 m^*} \quad \text{Equation S1}$$
$$\varepsilon_{\infty} = 9; \quad N_h = 1.05 \times 10^{22} \text{ cm}^{-3};$$
$$m^* = 0.8 m_e; \quad \gamma = 0.8 \text{ eV}; \quad \hbar\omega_p = 4.25 \text{ eV}$$

ε_{∞} being the permittivity of the material in the limit of high frequency, i the imaginary unit, ω_p the plasma frequency of the material, γ its damping parameter (as estimated from the full width at half maximum of the absorption band), e the elementary charge, ε_0 the vacuum permittivity, m^* the reduced mass of the charge carriers (holes), and m_e the electron mass. The parameters were chosen to replicate the experimental results (Figure 1 in the main body), while remaining consistent with the range of values reported for the plasma frequency in the literature.^{1,2}

The optical response of CuS nanoparticles has been calculated within a classical framework, solving Maxwell's equations for small spheres with complex permittivities modeled *via* the Drude model. The computations were performed using the Finite Element Method, as implemented in the commercial package COMSOL, although the nanoparticles are small enough to be also well described as dipole-like excitations under the quasi-static approximation.³ These calculations consider a single CuS nanoparticle surrounded by a

homogeneous matrix of non-absorbing dielectric. In order to account for the molecular coating with mPEG, its refractive index has been included through the simple approximation $\epsilon_{\text{matrix}} = (\epsilon_{\text{solvent}} + \epsilon_{\text{glycol}})/2$, where the values for the solvent dielectric constants were $\epsilon_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = 1.33^2$, $\epsilon_{\text{DMF}} = 1.43^2$, $\epsilon_{\text{DMSO}} = 1.47^2$ and $\epsilon_{\text{glycol}} = 1.455^2$.

Numerical simulation of the heat conversion efficiency

For the case of 7 nm CuS nanoparticles ($S/\text{Cu} = 1.00$), electrodynamic calculations using the Drude model to describe the material permittivity estimate the scattering of the nanoparticles to represent less than 0.2% of the total nanoparticle extinction in the spectral range examined experimentally (806 to 970 nm, Figure S11). Consequently, under this theoretical description we can assume that the plasmon energy is fully dissipated to heat through the collisions of mobile carriers with the atomic lattice. This reasoning would suggest that the HCE for CuS nanoparticles should approach values of 100%.

The central expression employed to calculate the HCE of different materials⁴ (displayed in the main body of the text and reported here for clarity)

$$\eta = \frac{Q_{\text{ext}} - Q_0}{I(1 - 10^{-A_\lambda})} \quad \text{Equation S2}$$

contains three main elements measured in a system at thermal equilibrium: the external heat injected into the dispersion of nanoparticles in the solvent (Q_{ext}), the heat dissipated by the solvent alone (Q_0), and an expression in the denominator which accounts for the radiated power extinguished by the nanoparticles alone. The nanoparticle absorbance is given by $A_\lambda = \epsilon_\lambda cL$, where ϵ_λ is the molar extinction coefficient, c the molar concentration, and L the optical path. The λ in the subscripts is intended to remind us of the variables' wavelength dependence.

The energy converted to heat from the laser illuminating the solution has was with a theoretical computation of the absorbance ($A_{\lambda,\text{sol}}$) of the solution, under the simplifying hypothesis that neither solvent nor the CuS nanoparticles scatter any light,

$$\begin{aligned} Q_{\text{ext}} &= I(1 - 10^{-A_{\lambda,\text{sol}}}) \\ Q_0 &= I(1 - 10^{-A_{\lambda,\text{water}}}) \end{aligned} \quad \text{Equation S3}$$

where I is the total laser power impinging on the sample and the absorbance has been calculated using the Beer-Lambert law and assuming perfect plasmonic absorbers, *i.e.* no radiation is scattered across the beam path:

$$A_{\lambda,\text{sol}} = A_{\lambda,\text{water}} + A_{\lambda,\text{CuS}} = \mu_{\lambda}L + \varepsilon_{\lambda}^{\text{abs}}cL \quad \text{Equation S4}$$

Where μ_{λ} is the decadic absorption coefficient of water, with its values adapted from the data in Ref ⁵. The molar absorption coefficient $\varepsilon_{\lambda}^{\text{abs}} = \frac{N_{\text{A}}\sigma_{\lambda}^{\text{abs}}}{\ln(10)}$ taken to depend only on the absorption cross section of the nanoparticle, $\sigma_{\lambda}^{\text{abs}}$, obtained through electrodynamic simulations. Both μ_{λ} and $\varepsilon_{\lambda}^{\text{abs}}$ are wavelength dependent. The optical path of the cuvette is $L = 1$ cm and the molar concentration can be calculated from the number density of CuS nanoparticles (n_{CuS}), as $\frac{n_{\text{CuS}}}{N_{\text{A}}}$. The nanoparticle density has been taken to be $n_{\text{CuS}} = 3 \cdot 10^{13} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, a value consistent with an estimation, using Beer-Lambert law, of the experimental beam attenuation from the cross sections obtained computationally. The heating of a cuvette with only the solvent has been calculated in the same manner, just setting n_{CuS} to zero.

The physical system for which we have numerically solved the heat equation is a simplified one, in which we have neglected convection or any other fluid dynamics in the system and have only considered heat diffusion. Accordingly, the differential equation

$$\rho c_p \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla T \right) - k \nabla^2 T = Q_{\text{in}} \quad \text{Equation S5}$$

was solved to the special case with no velocity field, $\mathbf{u} = 0$. The remaining parameters are defined in Table S4. To mimic the experimental conditions, with constant magnetic stirring, we have imparted Q_{in} (either Q_0 or Q_{ext}) homogeneously to the whole solution volume from $t = 0$ s to $t = 1000$ s, then let the system cool by thermalizing with its environment. The environmental temperature has been set to $T_{\text{room}} = 293.15$ K, applied as a boundary condition to a cylinder surrounding the cuvette (Figure S12).

The simulated system has been allowed to cool after a heating time equivalent to that of the experiment, obtaining from this process the characteristic cooling time τ of the system. Both Q_{ext} and Q_0 were obtained for the numerical results by measuring ΔT and calculating τ , as per the procedure reported by Roper *et al.*⁴

Heating computations were conducted using numerical tools (FEM, as implemented in COMSOL) by solving the heat transfer equation in a system recreating the overall dimensions of the experimental cuvette. The material properties used in the computation are listed in Table S4, with the properties of the suspensions assumed to be the same as the solvent.

Computing heat at thermal equilibrium

To use Eq. S2 (Eq. 1 in the main text), we have to obtain values for the heat Q present at the numerator. As already stated in the main text, and here repeated for clarity, following the discussion in the source material for the method,⁴ we use the expression

$$Q = hA(T - T_{\text{room}}) \quad \text{Equation S6}$$

where T_{room} is the room temperature and hA is the product of the heat transfer coefficient and the area of the sample in contact with the environment, calculated as

$$hA = \frac{\sum_i m_i c_{p,i}}{\tau} \quad \text{Equation S7}$$

where m and c_p are the mass and heat capacity of the different materials that compose the sample, running through index i , and τ is the sample time constant, obtained by fitting the cooling part of the heating curves. This last variable provides information on how fast the system loses energy to the environment. Now, as briefly mentioned in the main text, how we choose to define the system is going to strongly impact the final reported HCE value. Let us consider two possible options when using a standard optical cuvette.

First, we could consider the sample to be solely the nanoparticle suspension, with the numerator in Eq. S7 dominated by the mass of the solvent. In this case, given that a significant volume of the cuvette is also brought to roughly the same temperature as the sample, our computation of Q , and thus of HCE, will be underestimating its real value. Table S5 illustrates this by comparing two simplified scenarios with the theoretical limit to HCE. The first set of

values are obtained in a simulated closed glass cuvette, filled with 1 cm^3 of solution heated homogeneously, and the whole system surrounded by air. The HCE is computed considering that the glass is not part of the system. The second set of values models only the solution, as a floating cube of liquid surrounded by air, and heated in the same conditions as the previous system. We can see from the second case, not including the glass, the measuring method gets closer to the theoretical limit.

Second, if we consider the full mass of the cuvette and introduce it in the calculation in Eq. S7, we will be most certainly overestimating the HCE, as the heated sample does not come in direct contact with an important fraction of the cuvette. Then, we can expect a gradient of temperature thorough the glass, making it unrealistic to consider it all at the same temperature as the solution.

SEM images of CuS nanoparticles synthesized with S/Cu of 2.00

Figure S1. SEM observations (A) of the sample synthesized using a S/Cu value of 2.00 return the presence of nanoparticles with different shapes, comprising large nanoplatelets and smaller quasi-spherical nanoparticles (D). In B and C a zoom of the areas indicated, respectively, with squares 1 and 2 in A are shown to highlight the presence of different morphologies in the sample.

Synthesis of CuS at different reaction temperatures

Figure S2. The reaction temperature influences the LSPR peak position (A), but it does not alter the crystal phase as can be inferred from the fact that the samples all retain the covellite crystalline phase (B).

Figure S3. Survey (A, D, G, J), and Cu 2p (B, E, H, K), Cu LMM (insets in B, E, H, K), S 2p (C, F, I, L) high-resolution spectra of the samples synthesized at 40, 60, 80, and 100 °C. In B, E, H, K the signal characteristic of Cu²⁺ is highlighted in red. In C the relative percentage of sulfide and oxidized sulfide species is reported (light green and light blue respectively).

Table S2. Summary of the results obtained from the analysis of the XPS spectra.

<i>Reaction temperature, °C</i>	<i>Cu 2p peak position, eV</i>	<i>Cu LMM peak position, eV</i>	<i>S 2p peak position, eV (relative percentage)</i>	<i>Cu-to-S ratio</i>
40	932.63	568.93	162.03 (64.8 %) – 163.63 (36.2 %)	0.95
60	932.30	569.00	162.00 (76.2 %) – 163.60 (23.8 %)	1.02
80	932.23	568.73	161.83 (83.8 %) – 163.63 (16.2 %)	1.05
100	932.20	568.56	161.96 (80.2 %) – 163.66 (19.8 %)	1.03

The survey spectra of the samples show the characteristic peaks of the species composing the CuS nanoparticles. In all the samples, the Cu 2p high-resolution spectrum shows the presence of copper in its singly oxidized state as confirmed by the position of Cu LMM peak. The weak satellite peak centered approximately at 942.5 eV in all the samples suggests the presence of negligible traces of Cu²⁺. S 2p peak can be fit with two doublets corresponding, respectively, to metal sulfide (green lines) and partially oxidized sulfide species (light blue lines): the considerable contribution from these latter species can be justified by the fact that the reaction is conducted in water and in air atmosphere, so that surface oxidation becomes a likely event. All the samples have the chemical composition typical of covellite (CuS), with a Cu-to-S ratio of respectively 0.95, 1.02, 1.05, 1.03 for the samples synthesized at 40, 60, 80, 100 °C. Following these considerations, the hypothesis that compositional variations from sample to sample influence the optical behavior of the synthesized nanoparticles can be ruled out.

Figure S4. The linear fit of the Tauc plot for the four samples synthesized at different temperatures (A) allows for the extrapolation of the energy gap (E_g) of the corresponding nanoparticles (B). The values are very close to one another: this stems from the fact that the samples have an identical composition and the energy gap value is heavily dependent upon the semiconductor composition: in fact, in these semiconductors E_g is prevalently determined by the presence of empty levels in the top of the VB.⁶ Even if the trend observed is a slight decrease of the energy gap when increasing the reaction temperature, the large error associated with this data elaboration makes it impossible to speculate about the size change.

Figure S5. TEM micrographs of nanoparticles synthesized at 40, 60, 80, and 100 °C (A, B, C, and D, respectively) show small particles of increasing size. The larger scale bars are 50 nm and the smaller are 20 nm. The irregular shape displayed in particular by the samples synthesized at 40 and 100 °C makes it hard to determine and compare the particle size distribution for the different nanoparticles. However, from the micrographs it is evident how the morphology and the size change in the four samples: the nanoparticles are progressively larger and those synthesized at 60 and 80 °C have a more regular quasi-spherical shape and a less broad size distribution.

Synthesis of CuS with different mPEG amount

Figure S6. The amount of mPEG introduced in the reaction environment was varied to investigate the effect of this molecule as a ligand in controlling the growth of the nanoparticles. The hydroxyl tail group and the oxygen atoms in the backbone of the molecule can all act as effective Lewis bases (electron lone-pair donors) to stabilize free copper ions in solution. This is true, even though the affinity of copper towards oxygen is low, if compared for instance with the one displayed from the transition metal towards thiol groups. The mPEG amount was observed to play a minor role in the CuS nanoparticle synthesis at the investigated conditions. Actually, even when a sub-stoichiometric amount of mPEG (0.25 g, 0.05 mmol) is present in the reaction environment with respect to Cu^{2+} (0.10 mmol), the number of oxygen atoms is in large excess with respect to the metal ions (each polymer chain counts approximately 110 – $\text{CH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-O}$ - repeating unities). Indeed, the variation of mPEG amount does not influence the optical properties of the synthesized nanoparticles: both intensity and profile shape are substantially identical in all samples.

Synthesis of CuS at different pH

Figure S7. As in all aqueous synthetic approaches, the pH of the reaction mixture plays an important role in controlling the properties of the final material. In the case under study, the pH of the aqueous solution in the presence of copper and mPEG is 4.6. The pH of the reaction mixture was adjusted using 1 M solutions of NaOH and HCl. The absorption features of the nanoparticles are not influenced much when the pH is lowered below 4.6 (A). This is in accordance with the XRD observations (B) that reveal covellite single phase when the pH of the reaction mixture was between 2 and 4.6. At higher pH a secondary phase appears, namely posnjakite ($Cu_4(SO_4)(OH)_6 \cdot H_2O$, PDF #01-075-1258). The appearance of this copper hydroxy-sulfate hydrate is justified in light of the stability diagram of hydrated copper species in aqueous environment (C, adapted from the work of Albrecht *et al.*⁷). At the copper concentration used in the synthesis (approximately 10^{-2} M), copper is present as a free ion below a pH value of 5, while at more alkaline conditions copper hydroxide $Cu(OH)_2$ starts becoming the stable phase. For this reason, part of the sample is composed of posnjakite, a hydroxy-sulfate. The presence of this secondary phase is not desirable, since it crystallizes in large crystals, as can be concluded from the narrow peaks in the corresponding diffractograms. For this reason, although the optical properties are still preserved from the samples synthesized at high pH values, these samples could not be considered good quality heat converters.

CuS without mPEG – SEM observations

Figure S8. SEM micrographs taken with different electron accelerating voltages (A – 20 kV, B – 5 kV, C – 1,25 kV) on a sample of CuS nanoparticles, synthesized following the procedure described in this paper without the addition of mPEG, do not show the presence of organic material on nanoparticles' surface. This behavior is in marked contrast with what is observed in the reference sample (Figure 2 in the main body of the text), thus confirming that the coating layer observed in this latter sample stems from the presence of mPEG molecules. The scale bars in the micrographs correspond to 200 nm.

Thermogravimetric measurements

Figure S9. Thermograms of CuS nanoparticles coated with different ligand molecules obtained in an atmosphere of air (90 %) and N₂ (10 %). In these oxygen-rich conditions, covellite (CuS) undergoes a series of oxidation events that result in the formation of different phases (from CuS, to Cu₂S, Cu₂O, CuSO₄ and, eventually, CuO).⁸ These transformations are accompanied by mass variations that ultimately lead to an overall weight loss of 28.3 % (as obtained from the thermogram of an uncoated sample synthesized in absence of mPEG). The organic material instead undergoes combustion, therefore the overall weight loss is given by the combination of the weight loss associated with both CuS and the ligand molecules. Thus, for an observed weight loss – Δ – in a coated sample, the fraction of organic fraction in the sample – w_{ligand} – is given solving the set of equations:

$$\begin{cases} w_{CuS} + w_{ligand} = 1 \\ 0.283w_{CuS} + w_{ligand} = \Delta \end{cases}$$

where w_{CuS} is the fraction of CuS in the sample. Using this approach, and the values of Δ reported in the figure, the percentage of ligand molecules covering the nanoparticle surface was estimated to be respectively: mPEG – 24.0 %, PEG-SH – 14.9 %, PAA – 34.2 %, BSA – 57.2 %, GSH – 19.4 %, cysteine – 13.7 %.

Photographs of CuS sols in different aqueous media

Figure S10. Photograph of CuS nanoparticles dispersed in PBS 0.1x (top) and PBS 0.1x + 10 % FBS (bottom). The sols of GSH- and cysteine-coated CuS nanoparticles were obtained in a 50 mM NaOH solution in order to promote the deprotonation of the carboxylic groups of the two molecules, thus imparting electrostatic stabilization of the particles in suspension.

Table S3. Results of the DLS measurements for sols of CuS nanoparticles coated with different molecules and dispersed in distilled water, phosphate buffered saline (PBS 0.1x) and PBS 0.1x with the addition of 10 % of fetal bovine serum (FBS). The average hydrodynamic diameter (D_H) is reported along with the polydispersion index (PDI).

	mPEG	PEG-SH	BSA	PAA	GSH	cysteine
	$D_H, \text{nm} / \text{PDI}$					
Water	35.5 / 0.351	29.3 / 0.415	62.5 / 0.421	46.7 / 0.346	16.6 / 0.463	10.6 / 0.484
PBS 0.1x	31.5 / 0.267	30.0 / 0.394	57.4 / 0.252	50.2 / 0.439	21.7 / 0.522	11.1 / 0.462
PBS 0.1x + 10 % FBS	58.6 / 0.364	34.5 / 0.461	58.8 / 0.410	37.2 / 0.332	27.2 / 0.560	11.9 / 0.628

The measured D_H values reflect the steric hindrance of the ligand molecules tethered to the nanoparticles' surface. Nanoparticles coated with cysteine and GSH (both small molecules composed of few atoms) have a diameter close to the geometrical one determined from TEM observations, while larger polymer molecules (mPEG, PEG-SH and PAA) and BSA return a much larger hydrodynamic diameter. It is of interest to observe the different behavior featured by mPEG- and PEG-SH-coated nanoparticles in the presence of FBS: the former particles experience a size increase, likely due to the exchange of the loosely bound mPEG molecules for proteins in solution, reaching a diameter compatible with BSA-coated nanoparticles. Instead, the more tightly bound PEG-SH appears to prevent the formation of a protein corona, as can be inferred from the negligible variation of the diameter of the system when passing from PBS to PBS+FBS. Therefore, CuS nanoparticles coated with PEG-SH molecules are of great interest in view of their foreseeable application as photothermal agents in biological media, since the lack of protein corona formation prevents tagging of the nanoparticles by opsonins, which would ultimately lead to premature clearance by phagocytes.

Discussion of FTIR spectra of mPEG-CuS and ligand-exchanged samples

From the comparison of the FTIR spectra of ligand-exchanged samples with those of pure ligand molecules, we were able to confirm the success of the surface modification procedure. As reported in Figure 2A in the main text, most of the vibrations specific to the ligand molecules are observable also in the spectra of modified CuS nanoparticles (grey shaded rectangles).

The spectrum of parent CuS nanoparticles coated with mPEG features the characteristic vibrations of the polymer chains. mPEG and PEG-SH have identical FTIR spectra, therefore it is not possible to discern between these two molecules simply from their spectra. Nonetheless, both mPEG- and PEG-SH-coated CuS nanoparticles show characteristic signals stemming from the etheric backbone of the polymer. BSA is known to readily create a protein corona around nanoparticles imparting great stability to the colloid. The presence of the protein on the NP nanoparticle's surface is suggested by strong signals in the spectrum of BSA-passivated CuS nanoparticles arising from hydroxyl ($\sim 3300\text{ cm}^{-1}$), alkyl ($< 3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$), carbonyl (1650 cm^{-1}), and amide groups (1500 and 1390 cm^{-1}). The spectrum of the PAA-coated sample features a broad alkyl C-H stretching below 3000 cm^{-1} , the characteristic carbonyl stretch at 1700 cm^{-1} , and multiple signals in the fingerprint region ($< 1500\text{ cm}^{-1}$) assigned to C=O, C-O and O-H groups. In the case of GSH, different moieties can act as anchoring groups (thiol, carboxylic group, amine) and the spectrum of CuS nanoparticles coated with this species shows ~~weak~~ signals – arising from vibrations of C-O and C=O groups – in the $1700\text{-}1200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ range along with a weak vibration around 3300 cm^{-1} stemming from N-H groups. Cysteine-coated sample is characterized by a number of signals below 1700 cm^{-1} – mainly coming from amine, carbonyl and alkyl groups – along with an amine stretching centered around 3170 cm^{-1} .

Heating-cooling cycles in water under 808 nm excitation

Figure S11. The photothermal capabilities of CuS nanoparticles are retained upon repeated heating-cooling cycles obtained under 806 nm excitation over the course of 9,000 s (*i.e.* 2.5 h)

Heating-cooling cycles in water under 808 nm excitation

Figure S12. Absorbance spectra (A) of CuS-PEG-SH, -BSA and -GSH samples, used for HCE estimation, with the indicated corresponding absorption values at 806 nm wavelength. Heating-cooling curves recorded under 806 nm laser irradiation ($power = 0.18 \text{ W}$) for CuS nanoparticles dispersed in water. The surface of these nanoparticles was capped with PEG-SH (B), BSA (C), or GSH (D). Experimental data were treated according to Roper's model to obtain the HCE value for the photothermal agents. In the insets, the fit of the cooling part is shown from which corresponding heat-dissipation time (τ) was obtained and used to estimate the heat-transfer coefficient h in Equation S7.

Computational modelling of CuS nanoparticles properties

Figure S13. The modelling of the dielectric permittivity using the Drude model allows to simulate the experimental absorption spectra of PEG-SH-coated CuS nanoparticles sols prepared in water, dimethylsulphoxide, and dimethyl formamide. Experimental and simulated absorption spectra are plotted with solid and dashed lines respectively.

Figure S14. Ratio of absorption cross section over the total extinction cross section of independent CuS nanoparticles with a diameter of 7 nm, as obtained from the numerical electrodynamic simulations. For such small nanoparticles, scattering represents a negligible proportion of their interaction with light.

Figure S15. Geometrical model for the system under study. The cuvette is placed in the middle of a cylinder to which the boundary condition of $T_{room} = 293.15$ K, has been applied.

Comparison of HCE values of various photothermal agents

Table S4. Comparison of the performance of the CuS nanoparticles presented in this study with other photothermal agents excitable in the NIR, reported in the literature. The table was expanded from Savchuk *et al.*⁹

<i>Material</i>	λ_{ex} , nm	<i>I</i> , mW	<i>HCE</i> , %
Hollow Au-Ag alloy nanourchins ¹⁰	808	1000	80.4
Hyperbranched Au-dopamine blackbody ¹¹	808-1064	0.33-1.00 (W/cm ²)	>80
Shuttle-like CuS superstructures ¹²	980	1 (W/cm ²)	72.6
CuS nanoparticles (<i>this study</i>)	806	180	71.4
Cu ₇ S ₄ self-assembled nano-superlattices ¹³	808	1 (W/cm ²)	65.7
Au nanorods-Cu ₇ S ₄ ¹⁴	808	0.9 (W/cm ²)	62
Au nanorods ¹⁵	815	151	61
Au/AuS nanoshells ¹⁶	815	161	59
Cu _{7.2} S ₄ nanoplatelets ¹⁶	980	290	56.7
Au nanorods ¹⁷	808	2000	50
Dopamine-melanine colloidal nanospheres ¹⁸	808	2000	40
Biodegradable Au nanovesicles ¹⁸	808	1000	37
Au/SiO ₂ nanoshells ¹⁵	815	163	34
CuS nanoparticles ²⁰	808	1.00 (W/cm ²)	31.4
Cu ₉ S ₅ nanoparticles ²¹	980	510	25.7
Au nanoshells ¹⁷	808	2000	25
Cu _{2-x} Se nanoparticles ²²	800	2000	22
Au nanorods ¹⁹	808	1000	22
Au nanoshells ¹⁹	808	1000	18
Cu _{1.8} S nanoparticles ²³	808	1890	16.3

Parameters used for the calculation of CuS nanoparticles' HCE

Table S5. Summary of the parameters used for the computation of HCE in this study, both with experimental and simulation temperature data.

	<i>Thermal conductivity (k),</i> $\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$	<i>Mass density (ρ),</i> $\text{g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$	<i>Specific heat capacity (c_p),</i> $\text{J}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$
Water	0.6	1.000	4.186
Heavy water	0.58	1.105	4.242
Glass (SiO ₂)	1.0	2.650	0.840
Air	0.025	$1.2\cdot 10^{-3}$	1.005

Table S6. HCE computed in different theoretical scenarios. The first two columns are calculated from numerical simulations, emulating the protocol for computing HCE experimentally, *i.e.* measuring the temperature of the solution at its center.

	<i>Sample in cuvette, in air</i>	<i>Sample in air</i>	<i>Theoretical limit</i>
Water, 806 nm	63.8%	91.4%	97.8%
Water, 970 nm	41.6%	55.8%	62.0%

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